

The Analysis of Triple Bottom Line Concept Implementation in CSR Program through Local Food Processing Industry

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Enjang Pera Irawan, S.Sos, M.I.Kom-Universitas Mercu Buana, Fakultas Ilmu Komunikasi

Abstract:

This research attempted to analyze the implementation of triple bottom line concept in CSR program through local food processing industry. This was done because there were still few CSR programs in Indonesia which are integrating aspects of the planet, profit, and people. Therefore, the method used in this research was the qualitative method with single case study design. The data for this research were collected through interviews and observations with CSR program managers and relevant stakeholders. The data were analyzed using reduction process, data presentation, and conclusion (verification) techniques. Then, the data validity was tested through data and source triangulation techniques. The CSR program implemented by PT Energi Mega Persada Tbk.(EMP) is a form of fulfilling company's moral obligations, to reputation-building strategies, operating permit motives, and sustainable business building strategies. The implementation of CSR applies triple bottom line concept that includes: 1) the aspect of people which empowers people, 2) the aspect of profit, which improves the economic welfare of society and eases the company's operating costs, and 3) the aspect of planet, which is managing the natural environment properly to help sustain the sago raw material availability. The positive impact of this CSR program is the improvement of environmental quality, the increase of the number of entrepreneurs in the company's operating area, the establishment of a more harmonious relationship between the company and stakeholders, especially the surrounding community. To improve CSR program implementation, the following measures should be done: 1) Increasing business management mentors with good business and communication competence, 2) Facilitators and mentors need to be equipped with communication and public relations competence, especially community relation competence, 3) To help improving sales, sago-based products need to be marketed on a well-known online shop.

Key Word: CSR, Triple, Bottom, Line

1. PREFACE

One of the advantages that must be developed continuously by the Company is the superiority in providing added value to the environment in the vicinity of company's operation so it may become a trusted partner for many parties, especially the community and government in developing the environment and human being in the environment. Therefore, the Company must commit to improving the quality of life through the development of programs that support sustainable development, including economic, health, education and environmental management aspects, by involving the care of workers, local communities, governments, and larger societies.

Constitutionally, Indonesia has applied a regulation related to the implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) that must be implemented by the company. This is reinforced by the provisions of Article 15 paragraph (b) of Law No. 25 of 2007 and Article 74 of Law No.40 of 2007. The core of the law explains that the company is obliged to carry out corporate social responsibility. However, regardless of whether or not a regulation exists, a company should essentially implement the CSR program. CSR is the commitment of a company or business entity to contribute to sustainable economic development with due regard to corporate social responsibility and focuses on the balance between attention to economic, social, and environmental aspects.

Ethics in business and corporate sensitivity to the public interest is, of course, the main factor in the implementation of CSR programs. If the company is less sensitive to its environment, then this leads to public resistance against the company. Indeed, the company should view CSR as a part of the public rights to be fulfilled. However, Frynas (2009) identifies that the implementation of the CSR program is part of a reason to meet the demands of internal and external corporate interests which include: 1) to comply with regulations, laws, and rules 2) as a part of the company's social investment to get a positive image 3) as a part of the company's business strategy 4) to obtain licenses to operate from the local community 5) as a part of corporate risk management to reduce and avoid social conflict.

Apart of whether CSR implementation is a part of the effort to comply with regulations is a part of business strategy, or indeed a part of the company's commitment to the public, in fact, the company's effort

in implementing CSR is increasing. Such evidence is shown through the CSR award events which are getting increasingly competitively. One of the companies that continue commit to implementing CSR activities is PT Energi Mega Persada Tbk. (EMP). The EMP seriousness in implementing the CSR was then rewarded with 4 PROPER GREEN awards which indicate that community development programs implemented by the company obtained a positive recognition from the government.

EMP's CSR program is engaged in the community's economic development sector, education sector, health sector, as well as infrastructure. One of the leading CSR programs implemented by EMP is the "Sago-based Food Product Development" program in Bagan Melibur Village, Lukit, Belitung Bay Sub-district, Merbau District, Meranti County, Riau Province. It proves that the program earned a Gold Award for Best Key Performance and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) from SKK Migas. This program is a part of efforts to improve the welfare of the community around the company.

Considering that EMP's commitment is quite serious in managing CSR activities based on improving economic, human and environmental quality, the researcher is interested in analyzing EMP's CSR activities in applying the triple bottom line concept. This concept is a CSR approach that prioritizes aspects of sustainable development including three policies, namely economic development (profit), social development (people), and environmental protection (planet).

Based on this explanation, the researcher is interested in how the elaboration of CSR program by balancing the three pillars of Triple Bottom Line concept covering economic development (profit), social development (people), and environmental protection (planet). Through this research, the researcher intends to understand how companies elaborate CSR programs by balancing the three pillars of the Triple Bottom Line concept covering economic development (profit), social development (people), and environmental protection (planet) so that the CSR program will achieve sustainable development process.

The results of this research are expected to provide various recommendations related to communication innovation on how the implementation of communication aspects in the process of synchronizing the triple bottom line concept on CSR programs implemented by companies, especially in EMP. In addition, this research is expected to provide inspiration and become a role model for companies that will implement CSR programs based on triple bottom line concepts for sustainable development. In terms of academic, this research is expected to be a reference for subsequent research(s) and can enrich the scholarship in communication, especially Public Relations, on the discussion of CSR program analysis.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Corporate Social Responsibility

According to Kotler and Lee (2005), CSR is a commitment to improving society to be better through discretionary business practices and contributions from company resources. Kotler and Lee emphasize discretionary components, which can be interpreted as a corporate volunteer in applying business practices that benefit the welfare of the society (Suyono, 2010: 24)

From some of these definitions, CSR can be interpreted as organizational or corporate commitments in giving contribution as a form of social responsibility to the society, with the aim to meet the stakeholders' expectations, particularly the community in realizing sustainable development and to improve the welfare of the community.

There are various motives for companies in conducting corporate social responsibility (CSR). According to Michael E. Porter (2009), there are four motives that become the basis of the company's management in performing CSR, namely 1) moral obligation. In which the company must respect ethical values while doing business, 2) Sustainability. The company needs to be wise in meeting current needs without ignoring the needs of the future, 3) Operating permits. To obtain an operating license, the company needs to build "image" in order to gain government and stakeholder approval, and 4) Reputation. CSR is part of a strategy to raise brand and reputation to consumers, investors, and employees (Irawan, 2013)

Sustainable development covers three policy issues, namely economic development, social development, and environmental protection. John Elkington in the triple bottom line chart defines that the joint three development pillars of "people, planets, and benefits" which is the goal of development, are: 1) Corporate responsibility to maintain environmental capability in supporting the life sustainability for the next generation (planet), 2) a form of corporate responsibility to shareholders (profit), 3) the presence of the company must provide benefits to stakeholders and the general public (people), and 4) sustainable

development must be supported by a commitment to a balanced between economic, social, and environmental (sustainability development) (Rachman at all, 2011: 11)

The triple bottom line is a sustainable development concept that explicitly links between dimensions of objectives and responsibilities, either to shareholders, stakeholders and the planet. The concept of profit is a form of responsibility that must be achieved by the company, even by the economic mainstream that serves as the philosophical foundation of the company's operations. But not only profit is a priority, but the company must also fulfill its responsibilities to other aspects such as people and planet in order to achieve sustainable development.

The benefits of CSR programs are not only perceived by the community (stakeholders), but also by the company itself. Kurucz et. al. (2008) identifies at least four possible benefits categories that a company may obtain by engaging in CSR activities: (1) cost and risk reduction; (2) competitive advantage; (3) reputation and legitimacy development; and (4) results and benefits for the common good through value creation and synergic cooperation.

If it is done seriously, the company will get various benefits from CSR activities. Of course, the advantage is not the main purpose, but it is part of the positive impacts that arise from CSR activities.

2.2 Participation and Community Empowerment Concept

Community involvement in development should be the concept of development. To involve the community as a subject of development is a necessity, and this can be done through the community empowerment principle. Community empowerment can be done through a learning process in order to have access and control in development. Through this empowerment, the community is expected to have the ability to seize opportunities on available resources. In addition, the community is also able to play a role as decision makers and determinants in choosing and taking advantage of these opportunities.

According to McArdle, empowerment is a decision-making process by people who consistently implement the decision. People who have achieved collective goals are empowered through their independence, even it is a 'necessity' to be more empowered through their own efforts and the accumulation of knowledge, skills, and other resources in order to achieve their goals without reliance on external help (Ardianto and Dindin, 2011: 92)

Empowerment and participation are the main focus of the development process in recent years. Furthermore, Craig and Mayo explain that many countries are showing great attention to the community participation strategy as a mean of accelerating the development process. Therefore, an emphasis should be put on the importance of alternative approaches to development approaches initiated by empowerment processes (Ardianto and Dindin, 2011: 4)

The success of community empowerment-based development is closely related to the community participation. Craig and Mayo state that participation is an important component in generating independence and empowerment processes. The process is done cumulatively so that the more skills a person has, the better the ability to participate (Ardianto and Dindin, 2011: 92)

Paul states that empowerment and participation are really potential strategies to improve economic, social, and cultural transformation. This process will eventually create a people-centered development. One of the international agencies, the World Bank, for instance, believes that the community participation in the third world country is an effective mean of reaching the poorest people through raising the spirit of life to help themselves (Hikmat, 2001: 4).

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is a qualitative method with single case study design. A single case study has three rationalizations: first, once the case states an important case in testing a well-constructed theory; secondly, the case presents an extreme or unique case; and third, it is a disclosure case (Yin, 2011: 46). The uniqueness of the CSR program implemented by PT. Energi Mega Persada, Tbk (EMP) is the CSR program that refers to the potential of the region, as well as the aim to balance economic development (profit), social development (people), and environment protection (planet). In addition, pre-research results show every time the programs run; the operational costs are getting lower, in line with the level of conflict with the community. In this research, the researcher seeks to observe, understand and analyze the implementation of the program.

The data is collected through interviews and observations with relevant sources and related to CSR activities undertaken by EMP. In addition, the researcher will also collect data through field observation. In addition, this research is supported by secondary data obtained from offices, books (literature) or other parties who provide data closely related to the object and purpose of the research. The data taken are data that contains the value of information related to CSR activities undertaken by the EMP, be it from websites, books, documents, photos, etc.

The interviewees in this research are chosen using purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is a technique for determining samples with certain considerations. For example, when doing research on the quality of food, then the sample is a person who is a food expert. This sample is more suitable for qualitative research, or any research that does not generalize (Sugiyono.2004:124). Selected interviewees include EMP's CSR Coordinator, CSR Technical implementers, EMP Public Relations, and communities involved in CSR programs in Meranti Islands.

The data analysis techniques according to Miles and Huberman include three concurrent activities: data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion (verification) (Basrowi.2008:209.). To determine the validity of the data, the researcher runs a triangulation technique. Triangulation is a data inspection technique that utilizes something else outside the research data for checking purposes or as a comparison. Denzin distinguishes four kinds of triangulation as verification technique that utilizes the use of sources, methods, investigators, and theories (Moleong, J.Lexy, 2013:330). The triangulation technique used in this research is the triangulation of data and sources. Through the data, the researcher compares the result of the interview with the supporting data, then for the triangulation of source, the researcher compares and checks the degree of confidence of the information obtained by: (1) comparing the observation data with the interview result data (2) comparing the consistency of the interviewees reply by comparing what they say in public for example, by what is said personally (3) comparing one's perspective, with others in his team.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Reasons for CSR Program Implementation

The sensitivity of PT Energi Mega Persada Tbk.(EMP) in viewing the potential natural resources, as well as the company's commitment to encouraging the surrounding community towards economic independence becomes the reason for the company to develop CSR programs that empower community based on the abundant natural resources potential, yet still paying attention to the nature sustainability itself.

In general, CSR programs implemented by EMP include programs that encourage people to sustainable development, covering economic, health, education and environmental management aspects. In particular, for CSR program for community development in sago processing as a local processed food industry, the company considers that this extraordinary natural potential can be an opportunity to create new jobs. In addition, the Meranti islands have the potential and natural resources suitable as a basis for sago processing. This potential must be seen and made an opportunity to improve the economic prosperity of the community.

In addition, EMP also views government regulation as important, where CSR programs are certainly not only part of the company's commitment in empowering the community, but also a part of the company's obedience in running and complying with legislation set by the government, specifically those listed in Law No. 40 of 2007 on Limited Liability Companies, Chapter V Social, and Environmental Responsibility .Thus, various stakeholders, especially the government and community, indirectly can provide legitimacy to the company's operational activities.

The awareness of the importance of integrating people, planet, and profit elements in CSR program is also thought by EMP. It is realized by applying the concept of triple bottom line in CSR program of the local processed food industry. This concept is important because environmental and socio-economic issues in society can affect the company's operations. For example, when the company does not pay attention to the biophysical environment, this will have an impact on the potential for environmental damage that may disrupt the company's operations. In addition, the company's image and reputation in the eyes of the public will be harmed. This certainly can undermine the company's profits.

Not only paying attention to the nature issues, but the company also takes into account the socio-economic issues in society. The poverty caused by ignorance enables people to commit various harmful actions such as timber theft and forest destruction. Certainly, this condition will disrupt the company's operations, especially for companies that operate close to the forest. In addition, a fatal impact may occur. In

several cases, people looted the company's assets. This is certainly very disturbing and detrimental to the company.

The research findings show that the orientation and motive of CSR implementation through the application of triple bottom line concept refers to four things: 1) a part of the moral obligation, in which the company contributes to empowering society (moral obligation), 2) an effort in building a reputation. In this context, CSR is part of efforts to communicate corporate commitment as a company that cares about stakeholders and the environment, 3) an effort to obtain operating licenses. CSR program implementation is a form of corporate compliance to applicable laws and regulations, as well as efforts to obtain permission from the government, and 4) a part of corporate strategy in creating and managing business sustainability. Sustainability means meeting current needs without neglecting future needs. The easiest example is the environment. With the improvement of the environment, there will be no immediate economic benefits. If it's theoretically studied, this condition is in accordance with the concept of CSR motives expressed by Michael E. Porter (2009), which are the motive of moral obligation, the motive of an operating license, reputation motive, and sustainability motive (Irawan, 2013).

The perspective of sustainable development explains that the company is not limited to trying to commit and contribute to society through its CSR program, but also sees that the program is a part of an effective and efficient investment to support the achievement of sustainable development. To obtain the sustainable development, CSR programs must mobilize elements of people, planets, and profit in an integrated entity.

Rogers (2001) reiterated similar statement, saying that in order to create a company with true sustainability vision, all parties involved in the company need to have a better understanding of what "sustainability" means. There needs to be an extension of the company's orientation, from a financial orientation to a wider perspective of giving a positive impact on the environment (world) and society. Elkington (1997) explained one of the methods of sustainability measures is to use a triple bottom line covering people, planets, and profit (Jackson, 2011).

Of course, it is very logical when EMP designs a CSR program based on community empowerment through sago processing as the local processed food industry. This program is not only the company's commitment to contribute to the community, but also a part of the company's strategies in maintaining business continuity with integrated CSR program development strategy to develop the quality and capacity of society, ranging from social, economic, and environmental aspect towards sustainable development.

4.2. Implementation of Triple Bottom Line Concepts

The implementation of CSR in the form of sago industry processing program as a local food processing industry initiated by EMP is a CSR program that refers to the concept of the triple bottom line which includes people, planets, and profit. In this context, the company through its CSR program tries to synergize sustainable development activities by strengthening the community's economy, enhancing the community's ability to exploit natural resources, by not separating from environmental maintenance activities. Sago industrial processing program has at least been growing new entrepreneurs and managed to produce superior products of various processed sago cakes as food souvenirs from Riau.

The community plays an active role in the implementation of such CSR program. They are really involved from beginning to end on CSR program implementation. It is intended that the CSR program is not solely important for the program's founder, EMP, but also deemed important by the society because it suits their needs. The stages of CSR implementation by EMR include four stages, consisting of building joint commitment in the company's internal, social planning, building commitment with related stakeholders, and preparation of regional economic development agenda.

The first stage is building a shared commitment within the company. The shared commitment is pursued through focus group discussion (FGD) activities internally. The FGD aims to build commitments from all employees in implementing the CSR program seriously, as well as ensuring that the CSR program is in synergy with the company's operational activities. The commitment of all employees is one important factor in supporting the implementation of a sustainable CSR program. If the internal company as the initiator of the CSR program is not committed seriously, then it is difficult for the CSR program to be implemented sustainably. Therefore, internal corporate commitment is the first factor that must be built and strengthened.

The second stage is social planning. Activities undertaken in this activity is to do social mapping using participatory rapid community appraisal (PARCA) implemented in all villages / sub-districts which became the first-tier area of one company. This is done so that the community development program is in accordance with the demands. In addition, this social planning also seeks to ensure that the development program can synergize with the company's operational activities through employee engagement in its implementation. Therefore, the social planning stage is also done through the FGD process involving internal company and local stakeholders around the operation area, ranging from business actors, NGOs, government elements (villages, districts, counties/cities, and provinces) even with local universities. FGDs are conducted in collaborative ways to local economic development with industrial cluster methods.

The third phase is building commitments with relevant stakeholders. After the internal FGD is completed, an external FGD will be done in a collaborative approach to local economic development with industry cluster methods. The next step is to build a shared commitment to the formation of Working Group (POKJA). The FGD and the Working Group (POKJA) involved local stakeholders around the operation area, ranging from business actors, NGOs, government elements (villages, districts, counties/cities, and provinces) even with local universities. In the FGD, all stakeholders decided and agreed to implement the CSR program based on community empowerment with high commitment, which is done through various agreements.

The fourth stage is the preparation of regional economic development agenda. From this collaborative FGD, the development of local economy will produce an integrated regional economic development agenda in the short, medium and long terms. The FGD also agreed to establish a Working Group (POKJA) as a multi-stakeholder collaborative body that will oversee the collaborative agendas that have been developed. The social mapping document and the collaborative regional development agenda drafted by the Working Group serve as references for the company in implementing community development programs, which are in accordance with the aspirations of the community instead of the company's plan.

At this stage, the Working Group seeks to collect data such as 1.Data collection of specific business actors, 2. data collection for farmers/cultivators, 3. Data collection for plantation land. The social mapping document and the collaborative regional development agenda drafted by the Working Group serve as references for the company in implementing community development programs, which are in accordance with the aspirations of the community instead of the company's plan.

After the data are collected, the Working Group started looking for new entrepreneurs, conducting product sales training and sales promotion training, conducting an internship with the merchant, marketing, optimizing outlet at Meranti port, promoting in Community Radio, as well as performing sago land maintenance. From the FGD results, one of the potentials that can be developed by the community through CSR program is the community development in processing sago as processed local foods, ranging from processing to marketing. In addition to processing sago, the community is given the competence of how to preserve sago tree as a raw material for this local food industry.

Of all the series of CSR programs, one of the Working Group's most difficult challenges is to communicate and convince the public, especially the youth, to engage in community empowerment programs through sago processing as the local processed food industry. It's certainly not easy to change the mindset pattern to be an entrepreneur. Uncertainty and risks of entrepreneurship become one of the concerns. Therefore, EMP needs to multiply and spread a team of mentors who have an entrepreneurial experience to communicate and convince the public.

It is expected that the more business mentor incorporated in the Working group, the higher the interest and participation of the community to become an entrepreneur in local food processing industry. If it's done professionally, the sago processed business as local food is very potential to develop into a regional specialty, as well as becoming a promising business. Therefore, mentors will not solely have business skills, but also the competence of communication and motivation so as to open the minds of the community.

Referring to the CSR program implemented by EMP, the company has strived to the corporate social responsibility program by integrating the community empowerment aspect, in which the community is empowered to see the various potentials and resources that can be utilized (people). By doing the empowerment, it is expected to result in an improved economy of the society in community economy (profit).In addition, the company also keeps maintaining the environment, in this case, the way to maintain

and manage the ecosystem particularly sago tree (planet), so the CSR program can run in the long term and support the sustainable development for both CSR program implementers and the community (sustainability development).

The concept of sustainable development practiced by EMP is in line with Goel (2010) that sustainable development is a part of efforts to meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The way it is done is by trying to integrate three paths: economic, social, and environment (Alhaddi, 2015). It is clear that the implementation of triple bottom line concept in CSR program implemented by EMP is oriented towards the sustainable development that seeks to balance between profit, nature sustainability, and community empowerment. In addition, the implementation of triple bottom line concept is a part of the responsibility for future generations.

The explanation related to triple bottom line concept is in accordance with the EMP's CSR program, which is a part of the effort to empower the community in exploring various business and economic opportunities through the utilization of natural resources in Meranti Regency, which one of them is sago. With the guidance of how to process sago into local foods, the community around the EMP experienced improvements in their economy. Not only pursuing economic aspects, but EMP also seeks to educate the community to be able to maintain the environment, especially sago field in a good and environmentally friendly way. Given the skill of how to process sago and market it, and how to manage the environment (ecosystem) well, it will have positive implications on sustainable development that will be felt both by community and company.

Sustainable development is basically an output from the implementation of triple bottom line concept, where we can see the success of the company's business by measuring the achievements of three perspectives: people, planets, and profits (Elkington, 1998). In the pursuit of sustainable development, EMP implemented a triple bottom line concept that includes: 1). Giving knowledge and skills of how to utilize sago to the community as a local food processing industry, as well as in giving understanding in maintaining the ecosystem well, so that the sago trees productivity will increase. This is part of the aspect of community empowerment (people), 2). With the competence of how to utilize sago as a local food industry from processing to marketing, it becomes a part of efforts to encourage community economic improvement, and indirectly reduce the company's budget in giving charity (profit), 3). Understanding how to maintain the ecosystem well and how to care for sago properly, this can certainly encourage the improvement of environmental quality in the community (the planet).

Referring to how the triple bottom line concept is implemented, the company applies this concept in principle to provide added value to the existence of the company for the community, yet still properly maintain the environment and always consider the profit for the company in the longer term. The synergy of the management of this concept will lead to the realization of sustainable development which will increase the profit of all parties.

4.3 CSR Programs Impact

If it's managed properly, CSR program will have a significant impact on improving the quality of community welfare, maintaining the natural environment, as well as increasing profits for the company. But most importantly, CSR will provide a sustainable development process that will have a positive impact both for the company as the initiator and the community and other stakeholders as partners in the program.

Therefore, the CSR program should be able to lead to sustainable development processes (land, cities, businesses, communities, etc.) to meet current needs without compromising the need of future generations (Brundtland Report of the UN, 1987). One of the challenging factors, in order to achieve sustainable development, is to prevent the destruction of the environment without sacrificing economic and social justice (Rachman et al., 2011).

The implementation of sago industry processing program as local food is a form of CSR program that aims to encourage the process of sustainable development which includes efforts to strengthen the community's economy, improve the ability to explore the natural potential sustainably. However, such activity cannot be separated from environmental maintenance activities. Sago industrial processing program has at least been growing new entrepreneurs and managed to produce superior products of various processed sago cakes as food souvenirs from Riau.

Generally, the EMP's CSR program applies the concept of the triple bottom line as a meeting of the development pillars of "people, planets, and profits." By thoroughly reviewed, the elements of people is reflected in the high involvement by the community in the EMP's CSR program. The community involvement is seen from the CSR implementation process from beginning to end, such as 1) to engage in social planning. At this stage, people in all villages/sub-districts that become the ring area of a company are involved as business actors, NGOs, governmental elements (village, district, regency/city, and province). Even local universities are involved in the identifying various problems and potentials that can be developed through CSR program approach. 2) The community is invited to commit to synergize CSR programs together by forming Working Groups (POKJA); 3) the community incorporated in POKJA are then involved in the process of preparing regional economic development agenda. POKJA also accompanies various ranges of activities, from processing to marketing. In addition, POKJA also provides assistance and guidance of sago tree conservation as raw material for the local food industry.

Not only for the people, but EMP's CSR program also is trying to manage the element of the planet by managing and preserving the environment, especially the care of sago trees by using certain approaches and methods. The POKJA provides community understanding and skills on how to manage and conserve sago trees. This is done by training the community to utilize sago as a local food processing industry, yet still paying attention to environmental sustainability, so that this activity can run in the long term. Upon this effort, The EMP's CSR team achieved 4 Proper Greens in 2014, including EMP Semberah, EMP Gelam, EMP Malacca Straits SA, and EMP Bentu. This indicates that the community development program implemented by the company is in line with the Ministry of Environment program and CSR program has no longer oriented towards a charitable activity but is oriented towards sustainable development.

With the CSR program which reaches though people and the planet elements, this indirectly stimulates the increase of profit for CSR program implementers, as well as the community (target) of CSR program recipients. Such achievement in profit element is seen from the success of the partners which routinely becomes representative for Meranti Regency in the exhibition of processed food. In 2014 for example, the Government of Meranti Islands Regency held a Sago Nusantara Food Festival at East Parking Senayan, Jakarta on 3-4 May 2014. Such achievement certainly deserves an appreciation. In addition, the research on CSR programs in the field of economics shows that CSR programs implemented by EMP have impacts on economic improvement reaching 90%, then the community experienced an increase in assets as much as 65% (Juliana, 2014). From the results of this research, it can be concluded that the CSR program implemented by EMP indeed has a role in increasing economic independence of the community.

From a theoretical perspective, the EMP's CSR program is part of the efforts to empower people, in hopes of improving the economy (profit), while maintaining the environment (planet), so that CSR programs can run on a long-term basis. As stated by Elkington, the company is responsible for keeping the environment to support the sustainability of life for the next generation (planet), the company is also responsible for enhancing the economic capacity of the company to the shareholders (profit), and the presence of the company must provide benefits to stakeholders and broad community (people). With the fulfillment of the three elements of the triple bottom line, the CSR create a sustainable development with has balanced between economic, social, and environment (sustainability development).(Rachman et al., 2011: 11) .

The research findings show that the CSR program certainly does not only have positive implications on improving the quality of community welfare and improving environmental quality but also gives a positive impact on the business sustainability process in accordance with the company's expectations. Business sustainability can be seen by maintaining the company's assets and public acceptance of the company's operational activities. With reduced conflict and community resistance, the company's assets are maintained and can certainly minimize the cost of maintenance.

Generally, EMP's CSR program has many benefits for both companies and communities, as well as the environment. This is in line with Kurucz et al. (2008) notion who identified are four possible categories of benefits that a company may obtain by engaging in CSR activities: (1) cost and risk reduction; (2) competitive advantage; (3) reputation and legitimacy development; and (4) results and benefits for the common good through value creation and synergistic cooperation.

Other opinions also reinforce the argument that many of the benefits the company will obtain from CSR activities, which will ultimately build brand quality and strengthen consumer loyalty. It is as stated by

Dixon (2004) in which the performance of companies represents their commitment to stakeholders, the natural environment, and their respective economic advantages. As efficiency and innovation increase, including the presence of CSR concept, it may generate benefits that create competitive advantage and in turn lead to profitability, without sacrificing the environment. The corporate attention to social issues can be rewarded with brand acknowledgment from the community as well as loyalty.

It can be concluded that when a company is proactive to commit to solving various social and environmental problems in its stakeholder's vicinity, it will have a positive impact on the company, then the company is considered socially responsible. In this context, the scope of stakeholders is extensive, covering employees and managers, customers, suppliers, creditors, shareholders, governments, and the wider community.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1. CONCLUSIONS

The research results show that the Local Processed Food CSR program conducted by PT. Energi Mega Persada Tbk (EMP) is a CSR program that aims to empower the economy of the community, yet still paying attention to environmental aspects. The main conclusions from this research are:

1. The CSR program implemented by EMP is a part of the efforts to fulfill the company's moral obligations, a part of strategies to build a reputation, a form of corporate compliance with applicable laws and regulations, and a company's measure in maintaining business sustainability.
2. The triple bottom line concept becomes the reference in CSR program implemented by EMP. Within the people aspect, the community is fully involved in exploring the potential and given the skills to be used. Within the profit aspect, the company is helped in alleviating the operational costs. As for the community, they obtain the benefits of improved welfare and economy. In the aspect of the planet, the well-managed natural environment has resulted in the maintained availability of sago raw material.
3. CSR program through local processed food industry gives positive impact, among others: 1) environmental quality improvement, as indicated by achievement of 4 Proper Green by EMP, and 2) profit achievement as seen from the success of partners that routinely become representative of Meranti Regency in the exhibition of processed food, 3) giving reward both financial and non financial for EMP.

5.2. Suggestions

Based on the research findings, the researcher suggested that the company considers the following matters:

1. Improve community participation in CSR program. Therefore, it should be formulated in a collaborative way how to build awareness, understanding, and external awareness through an integrated public relations strategy for corporate communication team.
2. To increase community participation in the CSR program, it is recommended that EMP increase the management team for sago processed business mentors so that their presence can increase the interest of the community to become entrepreneurs in the processed sago as a local food.
3. Facilitators and mentors who are members of POKJA are advised to be equipped with knowledge and communication skills, as well as public relations skill, especially the competence of community relations. This can be useful in facilitating communication with stakeholders, especially the heterogeneous community.
4. To assist the promotion of processed sago as a local food for the wider community, it is recommended that sago processed products are not only marketed conventionally and through social media, but also on the reputable online shop.

References

- i. Alhaddi, Hanan . *Triple Bottom Line and Sustainability: A Literature Review. Business and Management Studies Vol. 1, No. 2; September 2015 ISSN 2374-5916 E-ISSN 2374-5924 Published by Redfame Publishing.*
- ii. Ardianto dan Dindin M. Machfudz. 2011. *Efek Kedermawanan Pebisnis dan CSR. Jakarta: PT Elex Media Komputindo.*
- iii. Basrowi. 2008. *Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif. Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta.*
- iv. Dixon, T. *Corporate Social Responsibility, the Triple Bottom Line, Standardization and Brand Management in Houston, Texas. Master thesis in Sustainable Development at Uppsala University, No. 207, 2014, 34 pp, 30 ECTS/hp*
- v. Frynas, JG. 2009. *Beyond Corporate Social Responsibility, Oil Multinationals and Social Challenges. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.*
- vi. Hikmat, Harry. 2001. *Strategi Pemberdayaan Masyarakat. Bandung: Humaniora Utama.*
- vii. Irawan, Pera Enjang. *Corporate Social Responsibility Program On The Basis Of Community Development. Universitas Padjadjaran (Jurnal). 2013*
- viii. Jackson, Aimee. *Sustainability and Triple Bottom Line Reporting – What is it all about?. International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology. Vol. 1 No. 3; November 2011*
- ix. Sugiyono. 2004. *Metode Penelitian Administrasi. Bandung: CV. Afabeta.*
- x. Moleong, J. Lexy, 2013. *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif Edisi Revisi. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.*
- xi. Rachman, Efendi dan Wicaksana. 2011. *Panduan Lengkap Perencanaan CSR. Jakarta: Penebar Swadaya.*
- xii. Suyono, Eko. 2010. *Corporate Social Responsibility antara Harapan dan Realitas. Bandung: UNPAD PRESS.*
- xiii. Yin K. Robert. 2011. *Studi Kasus: Desain & Metode. Penerjemah: M. Djauzi Mudzakir. Jakarta: PT RajaGrafindo Persada.*